

REBECCA

Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions
supported by causal analysis of multi-source data

D8.1 – Project website and dissemination material

Project Acronym:	REBECCA
Grant Agreement N°:	965231
Project Full Title:	Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions supported by causal analysis of multi-source data
Starting Date:	1/4/ 2021
Duration in Months:	48

Deliverable version	1.0
Date	21 August 2021
Nature of deliverable	Websites, patents, filling, etc.
Dissemination level	Public
Work Package	WP8 – Dissemination and communication
Lead Beneficiary	EHMA
Author(s) / Contributor(s)	Cristiana Grosaru (EHMA), Tina Hadzic (EHMA)
Status	Submitted

Document History

Version ¹	Issue Date	Status ²	Content and Changes
0.1	19 August 2021	Draft	First complete draft
0.2	20 August 2021	Draft	Updated Introduction and Conclusion sections
1.0	21 August 2021	Submitted	Finalised text

¹ Please use a new number for each new version of the deliverable. Use "0.#" for Draft and Peer-Reviewed. "x.#" for Submitted and Approved", where $x \geq 1$. Add the date when this version was issued and list the items that have been added or changed.

² A deliverable can be in one of these stages: Draft, Peer-Reviewed, Submitted and Approved.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

EHMA European Health Management Association

WP Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable 8.1 showcases the visual identity, the communication channels and the communication materials developed for the REBECCA project.

Regarding visual identity, a project logo was created via a consultation process. In what concerns the communication channels, social media accounts were created for the most relevant social media platforms and a project website was developed across a multi-phase process. Presentation templates, a project leaflet and a project poster template were created as communication materials.

All of these will allow the REBECCA project's communication to kick-off and the communication and dissemination strategy to be built on them, providing the necessary framework for the project communication and dissemination.

1 Introduction

The current document presents the visual identity, the communication channels and the communication materials developed for the REBECCA project. All of these were produced in collaboration with the project coordinator and the consortium partners.

As the project progresses, new materials and templates will be produced, and existing ones will be updated. All partners can access the latest versions through the REBECCA's Teamwork file repository.

1.1 Intended audience

This deliverable is intended for the persons developing and expanding the dissemination material of REBECCA. In addition, it provides a comprehensive reference for the templates, dissemination material and communication channels, useful for all partners of the REBECCA consortium.

1.2 Structure of the document

Following this introduction, Section 2 describes the visual identity of REBECCA; Section 3 documents the social media channels; Section 4 introduces the templates for presentations and deliverables; Section 5 presents the promotional materials; and Section 6 presents the REBECCA website. Finally, Section 7 concludes the deliverable.

2 Visual identity

A visual identity for the project has been developed to ensure a clear, consistent and recognisable brand for all project communications and to underline the project's objectives.

2.1 Project logo

The REBECCA logo was created via a consultation process with the project coordination team and all consortium partners. In the first phase of the consultation, EHMA designed and presented 7 versions of the project logo which were evaluated with the project coordinator. Two versions of the logo were selected and shared with all consortium partners in phase two of the consultation. Partners shared their preference and feedback via a [survey](#). Based on the results of the survey, the project logo was selected and finalised according to the feedback received.

The selected logo includes the following key elements:

- a pink ribbon, which resembles to the international symbol of breast cancer awareness, underlining the support that the project aims to bring to breast cancer patients;
- the two ends of the ribbon, one purple and one lilac, representing the two pillars of the project – 1) clinical research on complex chronic conditions and 2) support to breast cancer patients who have undergone or are undergoing breast cancer treatment;
- the acronym of the project.

The logo and the colour scheme will accompany the project during its duration, as a harmonised and consistent way of transmitting the project image to the public.

Figure 1: REBECCA logo

Figure 2: REBECCA logo with the full name of the project

2.2 Project branding

Table 1: REBECCA brand colours

Colour	Code
	HEX: #EA60A7 RGB (234, 96, 167)
	HEX: #BEACD2 RGB (190, 172, 21)
	HEX: #66528A RGB (102, 82, 138)
	HEX: #353A47 RGB (53, 58, 71)
	HEX: #EFEFEF RGB (239,239,239)

Table 2: REBECCA brand fonts

Main font	Alternative font
Uni Neue	Segoe UI
Uni Neue Thin	Segoe UI Semilight
	Segoe UI Semibold

3 Social media identity

The project's identity on social media remains consistent with the visual identity previously presented. The following social media accounts were created to ensure outreach to stakeholders and the general public:

- Twitter: @REBECCA_project https://twitter.com/REBECCA_project
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/74043627/>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/REBECCA-project-103192148666348>
- YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCY_F7QWMQLBCFA274S1ctVQ/featured

Figure 3: REBECCA Twitter page

Figure 4: REBECCA LinkedIn page

Figure 5: REBECCA Facebook page

Figure 6: REBECCA YouTube channel

4 Templates

In order to ensure widespread project recognition at conferences, workshops and other dissemination events, the following templates have been developed, reflecting the visual style of the logo.

Two versions of the PowerPoint presentation template were created:

Figure 7: PowerPoint template with a white background

Figure 8: PowerPoint template with a grey background

Likewise, the deliverable template developed by the project coordinator has been updated with the project logo and the format was edited to be in line with the visual style of the logo.

Figure 9: REBECCA deliverable template

5 Promotional materials

5.1 Leaflet

The REBECCA leaflet summarises the project, its objectives, the methodology that will be used and the project partners. With an easily accessible format and language, the leaflet will be used as a communication tool to introduce REBECCA to different audiences. The leaflet was developed in consultation with all project partners and the necessary changes were made based on the feedback received.

REBECCA
REsearch on **Br**east Cancer induced chronic conditions supported by **C**ausal Analysis of multi-source data

ABOUT THE PROJECT

REBECCA project aims at using **Real-World Data** to support **clinical research** on complex chronic conditions in the **post-treatment of breast cancer**.

REBECCA will combine clinical data with data obtained from multiple wearable, online behaviour and registry data to study the impact of primary and adjuvant cancer treatment on patients' quality of life and assess the value of **personalised patient monitoring as a means for improved patient care**. It will also demonstrate the extensibility of the project to other forms of cancer.

OBJECTIVES

TO IMPROVE CLINICAL RESEARCH ON COMPLEX CHRONIC CONDITIONS THAT CHALLENGE THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF BREAST CANCER PATIENTS

TO IMPROVE HEALTHCARE OUTCOMES FOR PATIENTS AFTER THE PRIMARY BREAST CANCER TREATMENT

METHODOLOGY

REBECCA will collect data from smartphone and smartwatch/band sensors, biobanks, including data from tumour and repeated blood sample analyses, images, social media, online behaviour data, open and commercial maps. Additionally, official statistics, patient-reported data collected through validated questionnaires in clinical settings and through mobile apps will be combined with clinical data, as well as patient and citizen registries, e.g. national registries of employment, insurance, hospitalisation, prescription drugs, etc.

The data will be analysed within **7 clinical studies** in 3 countries, Norway, Spain, and Sweden, involving over 650 individuals, and it will help **shape future guidelines and practices for post-cancer treatment**. Best practices resulting from the studies will be disseminated to researchers, public health and regulatory bodies throughout Europe.

PARTNERS

- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- Karolinska Institute
- Stavanger University Hospital
- Fundación para la Investigación del Hospital Clínico de la Comunidad Valenciana INCLIVA
- Centre for Research and Technology Hellas
- Harokopio University of Athens
- INTRASOFT International
- Eight Bells
- European Health Management Association
- Timelex
- The Breast Cancer Society Amazona
- Region Stockholm through Karolinska University Hospital

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 965231.

Figure 10: REBECCA leaflet

5.2 Poster template

A poster template was developed to support project partners at external events and conferences, where they can raise awareness on the REBECCA project. The poster template can include information such as background, objectives, methodology, results and conclusions. The content of the REBECCA posters will be defined on a case-by-case basis in collaboration with the partners that will represent the project externally. The template was developed in consultation with all project partners.

Figure 11: REBECCA poster template

6 Website

The REBECCA website, hosted under the URL www.rebeccaproject.eu, represents the main repository and communication channel for the project results and messages. It features a user-friendly and intuitive design dedicated to a large audience, which aims to ensure accessibility not only from a computer, but also from mobile devices such as tablets and smartphones.

The website was developed across five phases:

- Phase 1. Production of the website design through the collaboration between the web designer and EHMA;
- Phase 2. Consultation with the project coordinator and his team on the web design;
- Phase 3. Website set in by the web designer;
- Phase 4. Consultation with all project partners on the website structure and content;
- Phase 5. Integration of partners' feedback & launch of the website.

The website features a menu with 5 main sections, each one dedicated to a specific set of information:

- The "Home" page which provides an introduction to the project, the Work Packages and the consortium;
- The "About REBECCA" page, which goes more in depth about the project objectives and methodology. This section also contains five subsections with further details regarding the project: "Real-World Data in clinical research", "Objectives", "Work Packages", "Consortium" and "FAQ" ;
- The "Platforms" page presents the Rebecca 360° platform and the REBBECA apps, which will collect Real-World Data;
- The "News" page includes two subsections, one dedicated to the news items and one dedicated to the regular newsletter.
- The "Contact" page provides on one hand the contact details of the project coordinator and of WP8 Leader, and on the other hand, the possibility to get in contact with the REBECCA team via an online form.

Figure 12: REBECCA website homepage [part 1]

The screenshot shows the REBECCA website homepage. At the top left is the REBECCA logo. To its right is a navigation menu with links for Home, About REBECCA, Platforms, News, and Contact Us. Below the navigation is a main content area with a pink background. It features a headline: "The EU-funded project REBECCA taps into the potential of Real-World Data to support clinical research and to improve existing clinical workflows." This is followed by a paragraph explaining the project's goals and a group of diverse people wearing pink ribbons. Below this is a newsletter sign-up section with the heading "Sign up to our newsletter", a short description, an email input field, and a "SUBSCRIBE" button. The next section is titled "More impact of clinical research on breast cancer patients" and includes an illustration of a person surrounded by data and security icons, a paragraph of text, and a "FIND OUT MORE" button. The final section, "How we will do it", lists eight work packages in a grid: "User requirements and co-creation", "System design and integration", "360° Patient monitoring using RWD", "Causal inference and prediction using RWD", "Clinical studies complemented by RWD", "Improved patient outcomes through detailed monitoring", "Improving research and clinical workflows using multi-source RWD", and "Dissemination and communication". A "FIND OUT MORE" button is at the bottom left of this section.

Figure 13: REBECCA website homepage [part 2]

News
Find out about the latest REBECCA related news.

REBECCA
Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions supported by causal analysis of multi-source data

**New EU-funded project
REBECCA to improve post-treatment in breast cancer**

REBECCA, REsearch on BrEast Cancer induced chronic conditions supported by Causal Analysis of multi-source data, is a new project funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. REBECCA aims to tap into the potential of Real-World Data to support clinical researc...

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[VIEW ALL NEWS](#) →

The Consortium

The project brings together 12 partners from 7 European countries. Clinical and technological universities, industry leaders, public health experts, and patient associations will work together to shape guidelines and practices for post-cancer treatment.

[FIND OUT MORE](#) →

Get in contact

If you have a question or feedback to give us, visit our contact page.

[CONTACT US](#) →

Figure 14: About REBECCA page [part 1]

Consortium

REBECCA brings together 12 partners from 7 European countries, and is led by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki.

REBECCA Consortium consists of clinical and technological universities, industry leaders, public health experts, and patient associations who will work together over the course of 4 years to shape guidelines and practices for post-cancer treatment.

[FIND OUT MORE →](#)

FAQs

Have a question? Why not view our frequently asked questions page and find out more about the project.

[VIEW ALL FAQs →](#)

Get in contact

If you have a question or feedback to give us, visit our contact page.

[CONTACT US →](#)

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[Got it!](#)

Figure 15: About REBECCA page [part 2]

Figure 16: REBECCA platforms page

Figure 17: REBECCA news page

[Home](#) [About REBECCA](#) [Platforms](#) [News](#) [Contact Us](#)

Contact Us

Get in Touch

The REBECCA project team is here to answer any questions you might have. Reach out to us and we will try to get back to you as soon as possible.

We look forward to hearing from you!

REBECCA project coordinator

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Figure 18: REBECCA contact page

7 Conclusions

The current document showcased the visual identity (logo), the communication channels (website, social media accounts) and the communication materials (presentation templates, leaflet, poster template) developed for the REBECCA project. All of these will allow the REBECCA project's communication to kick-off and the communication and dissemination strategy to be built on them, providing the necessary framework for the project communication and dissemination.